

Quantum Interference and Underlying Cycling Based on p , i.e. $\exp(ipx)$

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The free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ represents a static pattern in all of space, whereas $\exp(i \int p dx)$ is more closely associated with the movement of the particle or photon. Experimentally, the actual motion (path) of the particle is important and so is $\exp(i \int p dx)$. As a result, a given constant p represents cycles in space and these change if one changes p . The length traversed is also a factor because it may not represent an integer number of \hbar/p .

If one has $\exp(ipx+i\text{phase})$, then $\exp(ipx+i\text{phase}) \exp(-ipx-i\text{phase}) = 1$ for any p . This value of 1 or uniformity applies to non-interaction of the single object with constant p . The impulse probability scheme is still given by $\exp(ipx+i\text{phase})$ and depends on the phase whether space is considered uniform or not.

It is possible, however, for a phase shift to occur due to an interaction (reflection at an $n_2 > n_1$ index of reflection barrier) or through $\int p dx$, to cite two examples. In the latter, both p and length are linked to cycling. Incomplete cycling leads to phase shifts. Thus, a particle interacts through $\exp(i \int p dx)$ and not $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ and so $\exp(ipx+i \text{ phase})$ describes the structure of space from the point of the view of that particle or for a particular probabilistic path as in 2-slit interference. If one compares two particles, even with the same p , a kind of interaction of probabilities we argue even though p may be the same, one may be shifted from the other due to previous interactions and so interact in space differently than the other even though $\exp(ipx+i\text{phase})\exp(ipx+i\text{phase}) = 1$ for both. We suggest that interference is then the consequence of a kind of interaction of probabilities at the $\exp(ipx+i \text{ phase})$ level, either between two different objects or the same object with two different probabilistic paths.

$\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(i \int p dx)$

We have suggested in previous notes that $x=x_0+n*\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n*\hbar/E$ leave the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ (for a free particle) unchanged. We then suggest a set of gradations in space and time with a corresponding probability such that $P_1(p_1,x)P_1(p_2,x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution, but this is static in space while a particle with momentum (photon or particle with rest mass) moves. Thus, $\exp(i \int p dx)$ seems more appropriate. In other words space is being considered in terms of a cycling with gradations of \hbar/p . This begs the question: What happens if one does not complete a cycle? In such a case, one does not have $\int p dx = 2*3.14$, but rather a phase. This shifts the cycling pattern in space (which is the same as a physical impulse probability scheme we argue), although \hbar/p remains the same. Simply shifting the probability pattern does not change $\exp(ipx+i \text{ phase}) \exp(-ipx - i\text{phase}) = 1$, but if two probabilities “interact” (i.e. interfere) then there are consequences.

Probabilities may interact through an OR situation, but physically this may mean interference between two particles or a situation in which two probability paths are created in space as in 2-slit interference. $\exp(ipx)$ has a unit modulus because there is a constraint on its real and complex functions, namely that the square of each add to 1. An OR (add) or average of two results $\exp(ipx + i\text{phase}_1) + \exp(ipx + i\text{phase}_2)$ breaks this constraint and leads to different amplitude lengths over x . This leads to the usual interference pattern.

Examples of Interference Cases

We consider a few cases here. Two-slit interference is a well-known one for which one has two different paths in space leading to the same point on a screen far away, both following $\exp(ipr(\text{along path}))$ so one has: $\exp(ipr(\text{along path 1})) + \exp(ipr(\text{along path 2}))$.

A second example is a free particle which is created at some point x_0 . This breaks the symmetry of all space by giving preferential treatment to this one x_0 point and so one has $\exp(i\int p dx)$ where x_1 begins at x_0 and ranges to x . In other words $\exp(ipx)$, for a given p , represents a static uniform pattern in space, but physically there are interactions/obstacles which disrupt this pattern. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ describes the interaction probability of a particle, this disruption is important.

For a single particle bound state, $V(x)$ leads to various $\exp(ipx)$ s interfering in $W(x) = \sum p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. There is no phase shift here because there is no specific obstacle at any special x_0 point (or set of x_0 points) if $V(x)$ is written as: $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

We now consider the case of one dimensional -reflection-refraction with two junctions, one for n_1 - n_2 and the other for n_2 - n_3 such that $n_3 > n_2 > n_1$. The n_1 - n_2 junction is separated by a length L from n_2 - n_3 .

We first note that one may consider $\exp(ip dx)$ for the first junction and make $\exp(ipdx)$ s and their first derivatives continuous. This leads to solving the problem with $x_0=0$ at this junction. One may note that by using dx , one has $x_0=0$ as one considers the incident, reflected and refracted ray at the same point which may as well be 0, i.e. all originate at this point so to speak, but with different momenta.

A refracted ray will have a momentum of p_2 and travel a length L before reflecting at the n_2 - n_3 junction (and picking up a phase shift of 3.14). It will then become an incident ray moving with $-p_2$ at the n_2 - n_1 junction and refract out into n_1 having $-p_1$, but also a phase shift $2p_2L$. As a result, this is an example demonstrating how a phase shift is linked with dynamic motion.

The incident photon in n_1 may have an arbitrary phase $\exp(i \text{ phase})$. This carries over to all other rays in the problem and so can be set to 0. The first reflected photon, at the n_1 - n_2 junction, then receives a 3.14 phase shift because $n_2 > n_1$.

The photon which refracts receives p_2 and so cycles according to this momentum. It also picks up a phase of 3.14 when it reflects at the n_2 - n_3 junction. The reflected p_2 then returns to the n_2 - n_1 junction and refracts, coming out with n_1 and an extra phase relative to the first reflected photon of:

$$2p_2 L \quad ((1))$$

Thus, one has two rays with $-p_1$ in medium n_1 , but one underwent a different interaction history than the other. This gave it a phase shift which changes its impulse probability profile.

It is not necessarily the interaction history which is important, but rather that the interaction (changing p_1 to p_2) and hence the cycling period and the length L do not coincide with an integer number of \hbar/p_2 units. This then leads to an incomplete cycle when $-p_2$ refracts into $-p_1$ at the n_2-n_1 junction. The new $-p_1$ now carries this phase ((1)) which means that it represents a shifted interaction probability scheme which is not the same at a given x point as $\exp(-ip_1x)$ of the first reflected photon. (The phase shift of 3.14 has been dropped because both $-p_1$ photons carry it.)

Thus, if one has interference of the two $-p_1$ photons, one obtains:

$$\exp(-ip_1x) + \exp(-ip_1x + i 2p_2L) \quad ((2))$$

Even though each has a modulus of 1, adding two complex numbers breaks the constant modulus constraint and one obtains an interference pattern in space. Thus, the interaction pattern in space is not only dependent on cycling length \hbar/p , but also on any incomplete cycles which appear as a phase shift. These incomplete cycles may occur due to changes in p or not. The dynamics of the particle (possible paths that may be followed) is important, not just the \hbar/p gradation structure. The above problem is very similar to the case of two glass sheets at an angle with each other. One photon inside the first sheet reflects from $n_2-n(\text{air})$ and does not pick up a 3.14 phase shift. The other refracts, travels to the second sheet, reflects and picks up a phase shift of 3.14 as well as $p(\text{air}) 2L$ (another phase shift). These two then interfere as seen in experiments.

We also note that the Bohm-Aharonov effect is similar in that there is an interaction which creates a phase.

Thus, interactions and actual motion in space are important even for an $\exp(ipx)$ description of a quantum object.

Conclusion

We have suggested the emergence of \hbar/p from special relativity in previous notes. This leads to an $\exp(ipx)$ static probability function for interactions linked with uniformity in space, i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. Given that $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(-ip_1x)=1$ and $\exp(ip_2x)\exp(-ip_2x)=1$ simply means that p_1 and p_2 do not interact. 1 is the signature of noninteraction, while $\exp(ipx)$ represents an interaction scheme. If it is phase shifted, then this probability may interfere with $\exp(ipx)$ and yield an interference pattern because the interaction (p) probability is not the same for the two at any given x even though both treat space as uniform. We suggest that using $\exp(i \int p dx)$ is more consistent with the actual path taken by a particle (or possible path).

We consider the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon at an n_1-n_2 junction followed by an n_2-n_3 junction with $n_3 > n_2 > n_1$. We see that there will be two $-p_1$ photons in n_1 , but they will be phase shifted. Thus, the path taken by an actual photon is important as its cycling is affected by interaction (i.e. p_1 changing to p_2 for the refracted ray at n_1-n_2) as is L the distance between the two junctions. A photon (or free particle) seems to have a set cycling pattern imposed on space with \hbar/p gradations, but interactions may disrupt this pattern/cycle leading to phase shifts. These are physically important because $\exp(ipx+i \text{ phase})$ represents the impulse p probability at x . A different phase leads to a different complex probability at x . Adding

(OR) or even averaging to $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase})$ leads to a complex number which no longer respects the unit modulus constraint.